

1 **Agriculture and the Environment: Policy Approaches in Europe**

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14 **ABSTRACT**

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16 European agri-environmental policy has diverse and competing objectives. The Common
17 Agricultural Policy has been the main policy framework guiding the European Union (EU) and its
18 member states in the design and implementation of both mandatory and voluntary
19 agrienvironmental policy instruments. Voluntary agri-environmental schemes, which were
20 introduced in the 1990s, continue to play a central role in meeting the EU's environmental and
21 climate objectives. We find that these schemes have faced problems in achieving their objectives,
22 including their limited environmental impact, low adoption by farmers, and conflicts between their
23 environmental and income support objectives. The article also finds scant empirical evidence
24 concerning the environmental and economic impacts of the agri-environmental schemes. The
25 article concludes with a discussion of the lessons from past experiences and potential future
26 research and policy directions aimed at increasing the EU's achievement of agri-environmental
27 and climate objectives.

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30 Keywords: EU Agri-environmental policy, voluntary schemes, cost-effectiveness, water,
31 biodiversity, climate, participation

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33 JEL Codes: Q18, Q24, Q2

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35 **Introduction**

36 European agri-environmental policy remains dominated by the European Union's Common
37 Agricultural Policy (CAP). When first launched in 1962, the goal of the CAP was to stabilize both
38 agricultural produce markets and farmer incomes in Europe. Since then the CAP has been reformed

39 to also promote more sustainable paths for agriculture. Yet, despite many reforms aiming at
40 inclusion of environmental and biodiversity protection, as well as climate change mitigation and
41 adaptation, income support is still at the CAP's core (Latacz-Lohmann and Hodge 2003, Galati et
42 al 2015, Daugbjerg and Swinbank 2016; Alons 2017; ECA 2017, Pe'er et al 2019). Environmental
43 and climate objectives have been included by introducing first direct payments to incentivize
44 environmentally friendly practices in agriculture (1992 reform), and then cross-compliance to
45 achieve coherence between environmental policy and income support (2003 reform) (Brady et al.,
46 2009), and by greening, adding environmental conditionality to direct payments (the 2013 reform)
47 (Daugbjerg and Swinbank, 2016). According to the European Commission (EC) 'the CAP,
48 together with the Farm to Fork Strategy, does not only have the objective to reduce emissions but
49 also seeks to preserve biodiversity, and rural livelihoods, reduce pesticides use and pressure on
50 water quality and provide high quality food' (EC 2021, page 1). It remains to be seen to which
51 extent the member states (MS) will achieve these objectives.

52 The attempt to align agricultural market policy and income support with environmental,
53 biodiversity and climate policies makes the European CAP a large-scale policy experiment that
54 highlights many of the challenges central to agri-environmental policy design and implementation.
55 The diffuse nature of agricultural emissions coupled with asymmetric information about the
56 relationships between agricultural and environmental outcomes and the extent to which farmers'
57 efforts can moderate this, is a well-established policy challenge (Cabe and Herriges, 1992; Shortle
58 and Horan, 2017). Adding to this, the high variability in agricultural, environmental and social
59 conditions and objectives across European geographies, and multiple interacting policies has led
60 to the characterization of EU agri-environmental policy problems as a 'wicked' policy problem,

61 where any single proposed solution tends to generate a cascade of new problems (Kuhmonen
62 2018).

63 This wickedness and tension between income support and environmental support are observed
64 across the key policy fields, i.e. nutrient pollution control, biodiversity protection and also climate
65 change mitigation. Due to diverse societal priorities and agri-environmental and economic contexts
66 across Europe, targeting and differentiation across geographies and farmers are important for more
67 cost-effective implementation, but differentiation also leads to tensions due to perceived unfair
68 distribution of policy outcomes. An important instrument for the implementation of more locally
69 adapted water and nature conservation policy objectives has been the voluntary
70 AgriEnvironmental and Climate Schemes (AECS), supported by the CAPs rural development
71 programme. Some evident problems in the delivery of policy objectives by these schemes include
72 limited added environmental impact related to uniform choice of measures and compensation
73 payments at MS level, poor uptake amongst farmers, administrative costs as well as conflicting
74 objectives between implementation of environmentally effective measures and income support
75 objectives.

76 In the following, we give an overview of the European agri-environmental policy scene, in terms
77 of agricultural production systems, agri-environmental policies, and main challenges and
78 potentials. First, we introduce the origin of the CAP and the history of its reforms, the Directives
79 and initiatives to regulate water, biodiversity and climate as well as the documented impacts of
80 these and main barriers for implementation. We pay specific attention to the voluntary AECS, as
81 they offer a potential to match the schemes to the local conditions and policy objectives. Finally,
82 we discuss the lessons learned and outline some of the potentials for enhancing
83 environmentaleconomic effectiveness of under a reformed CAP.

84 **European Agricultural context and environmental problems**

85 Agriculture occupies more than 40 percent of the European land area, or approximately 245 million
86 hectares (EEA, 2020). Arable crops, in particular cereals, dominate, while pastures and mixed land
87 use make up 17 percent. While Denmark and Hungary, for instance, are dominated by arable land,
88 in Ireland and Malta pastures and mixed land uses abound. Countries like Sweden, Finland and
89 Montenegro are dominated by forests and scrubs. More than 60 percent of agricultural land is
90 managed by farms with medium-to-high intensity of fertilizer, feedstuff and pesticide inputs (EEA,
91 2020). High livestock densities are found in central and northern European countries, while to date
92 both crop and livestock density are much more modest in Eastern Europe. Demands on European
93 agricultural landscapes have been steadily increasing since the 1950s, with multiple and often
94 conflicting pressures on the management of land and water resources. Agriculture accounted for
95 11 percent of the total greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions in the EU-27 in 2019 (Eurostat, 2021),
96 and is the main source of biodiversity loss (EEA, 2017). In 2016, about half of the surface water
97 bodies in Europe) and one quarter of the groundwater bodies were not in good status, according to
98 the Water Framework Directive. Reducing agricultural loads of nutrients are key to achieve good
99 status (EEA 2020).

100 In the mid-1980s, policy focus had been on command-and-control regulation, initiated separately
101 by individual MS (Latacz-Lohmann and Hodge, 2003), with large (and often still remaining)
102 differences across Europe. Northern European countries introduced national legislation to prevent
103 nitrate pollution, the UK featured countryside nature conservation, while Southern Europe was
104 determined to grow agricultural production. EU policies met this diversity of foci with a twofold
105 strategy: direct regulation and framework directives requiring specific outcomes across all MS, yet

106 allowing MS flexibility in how to achieve these (Latacz-Lohmann and Hodge, 2003). The twofold
107 strategy is further elaborated on in the remainder of the paper.

108

109 **Agri-environmental policy in the EU – framework and implementation**

110 **The Common Agricultural Policy – the CAP**

111 The EU Common agricultural policy, the CAP, constitute 31 percent of the total budget for EU8
112 for the period 2021-27 (EUR 1 221 719.5 billion for the 7 years), a decrease from 38 percent in
113 2014-20, and 66 percent in the early 1980s. The CAP is organized into two pillars, where Pillar I
114 is for direct payments to farmers and was, previously, known as the market policy of the CAP.

115 Pillar II consists of support schemes for rural development, previously the structural policy of the
116 CAP. Pillar I has always consumed the largest share of the resources (in 2021, 77 percent of the
117 total CAP budget). Up until 1993, the CAP relied almost exclusively on indirect price support as
118 a means to stabilize and maintain farm incomes at a level considered comparable to other groups
119 in society. Guaranteed minimum prices (intervention prices) were set well above world market
120 prices. Threshold prices, set at a level above the intervention prices, were effectively functioning
121 as maximum prices. EU market prices would fluctuate between the two price levels. A system of
122 variable import levies ensured that imports did not enter the EU market below the threshold prices.
123 If EU market prices fell below intervention prices, the EU would intervene directly and buy up for
124 stock and/or subsidize exports directly.

125 As expected, this type of market management operating with artificially high prices contributed to
126 increasing production, resulting in huge production surpluses that had to be sold on the world
127 market using export subsidies. In the early 1980s, these alone consumed half of the CAP budget

128 (Swinbank and Daugbjerg 2017). Inevitably, the extensive use of export support caused tensions
129 with trading partners. On the insistence of the United States, agricultural trade became an integral
130 part of the international trade negotiations under the General Agreement on Tariffs and Trade
131 (GATT) in the mid-1980s and later under the World Trade Organisation (WTO). Eventually, the
132 EU realized that the CAP had to be reformed. In the 1992 Mac Sharry reform, minimum prices
133 were lowered by one third in the large arable sectors and 15 percent for beef and sheep meat.
134 Farmers were compensated for the price cuts through payments for areas where grain, oil and
135 protein crops were grown, and livestock farmers were compensated on the condition that they
136 would set aside 15 percent of their land, and limit livestock density. While set-asides had
137 environmental benefits, the main purpose was to curb surplus production. As part of the 1992
138 reform, voluntary environmental subsidies were introduced into the structural CAP policies
139 (Daugbjerg 1998).

140 The Agenda 2000 reform (agreed in 1999) was essentially a deepening of the 1992 reform, with
141 further reduction of guaranteed minimum prices, partially compensated by direct payments. The
142 structural policy was renamed ‘rural development policy ‘ and became pillar II of the CAP. It was
143 largely composed of already existing schemes; only limited additional funds were provided
144 (Daugbjerg and Swinbank 2009). However, over the years the funding for the second pillar
145 increased, currently (2021) consuming 23 percent of the CAP budget (European Parliament, 2021)
146 Pillar II has three components: (i) agricultural competitiveness (ii) sustainable management of
147 natural resources and climate action, and (iii) balanced territorial development of rural economies
148 and communities. Pillar II support requires 50 percent co-funding from MS. For the post-2022
149 reform, MS agreed in June 2021 to spend at least 35 percent of pillar II funding on
150 agrienvironmental schemes and animal welfare (EC 2021b).

151 The 2003 Fischler reform was aimed at the large arable sectors (grains, oil, and protein crops), and
152 mainly designed to enable the EU to give concessions in the WTO farm trade negotiations,
153 commenced 2001 in Doha, Qatar. A subsequent series of reforms brought smaller commodity
154 sectors into the single payment scheme. The Fischler and follow-on reforms decoupled the direct
155 area and livestock payments from the requirement to grow certain crops and keep certain livestock,
156 creating a single-payment scheme based on historical payment levels. MS were allowed to link up
157 to 25 percent of the payments to production requirements (Daugbjerg and Swinbank 2009). Great
158 care was taken to consider ‘the need to preserve farming incomes in a less trade distorting way’
159 (Commission of the European Communities 2002, p.3; see also Haniotis 2007). To be eligible for
160 the single payment, farmers were required to comply with environmental, animal health and
161 welfare, and food safety regulations (cross-compliance). A so-called health check of the CAP in
162 2008 led to further decoupling of direct farm payments and dismantling the remaining set-aside
163 requirement. Though the environmental benefits of set-asides were recognized, the original
164 definition as a production-limiting measure came to justify this decision, in light of the global food
165 crisis of 2007/08 (Daugbjerg and Swinbank, 2011).

166 The 2013 reform split the single farm payment into a basic (70 percent) and a greening payment
167 (30 percent). The latter was conditioned on farmers maintaining permanent grassland, practicing
168 crop diversification with at least three crops (two for small farms), and establishing ‘ecological
169 focus areas’ on 5 percent of their arable area (small farms exempted). For the large majority of
170 farmers, these requirements were easy to comply with. Thus, as a report from the European Court
171 of Auditors concludes: ‘The green payment remains, essentially, an income support scheme ‘
172 (Jereb et al. 2017, p6.). Further, some of the direct farm support decoupled in the 2008 Health

173 Check was recoupled (Daugbjerg and Swinbank 2016). Pe'er et al. (2017) concluded that the
174 greening, both design and implementation, is insufficient due to broad exemptions, lax requirement
175 for crop diversification and management, insufficient measures for climate as well as ineffective
176 options for Ecological Focus Areas (EFA).

177 The major change in the post-2022 reform agreed in June 2021 is the introduction of eco-schemes
178 by redesigning pillar I. Direct payments will be divided into a payment with conditionality and an
179 eco-scheme payment that must be minimum 25 percent of pillar I payments. Conditionality
180 includes the previous greening as well as cross-compliance requirements. The EFA measure,
181 which did allow farming activity, are replaced by a requirement to set aside at least 3 percent of
182 the arable area for non-productive purposes. MS are responsible for preparing strategic plans that
183 define which measures on individual farms should be eligible for eco-scheme support within their
184 jurisdictions, following guidelines issues by the EC (EC 2021a). While these changes are flagged
185 as a major reform, 75 percent of the direct payments will remain income support subject to
186 conditionality. Whether the eco-schemes component of the direct payments will be utilized by MS
187 to link payments to provision of environmental services with high impact, or whether they will be
188 watered down to an extent where all farmers can easily comply remains to be seen. In the latter
189 instance, eco-payments would essentially become income support in disguise.

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192 **Environmental policy objectives and the EU directives**

193 The directives of specific importance for achieving common European environmental, biodiversity
194 and climate objectives include the Nitrates Directive, the Directive on Sustainable use of

195 Pesticides, the Water Framework Directive as well as the Habitat Directive and the EU Climate
196 Law. The Marine Strategy Framework Directive and the Drinking Water Directive are also of
197 importance, but of more indirect relevance for the EU agri-environmental policy.

198 The Nitrate Directive (EEC/676/1991), introduced in 1991, aims to reduce and prevent ground and
199 surface water pollution by nitrates from agricultural sources, and by promoting the use of good
200 farming practices. Accordingly, MS have to designate Nitrate Vulnerable Zones (NVZs), defined
201 as areas likely to contribute to surface or groundwater contamination of 50 mg/L of nitrate (NO₃).
202 Mandatory measures are required, and uniform limitations on nitrogen application to land from
203 animal manure is an example of such measures (with exemptions given to individual MS).
204 Crosscompliance for the CAP basic funding was implemented on a voluntary basis in 2000, and
205 became mandatory from 2003. Farmers who violate cross-compliance are sanctioned with reduced
206 support, taking account of severity, extent, permanence and repetition of the non-compliance. MS
207 are obliged to define minimum requirements for the farming practices, taking into account the EC
208 defined Good Agricultural and Environmental Conditions (GAEC) (EC 1306/2013). MS are also
209 required to take into account the specific characteristics of the areas concerned, including soil and
210 climatic condition, existing farming systems and practices, land use, crop rotation, and farm
211 structures. Examples are buffer zones along water courses, soil protection measures and nutrient
212 balance requirements. Some countries have made assessments of cost-effectiveness of measures
213 prior to national implementation plans, but there are large variations between countries. EEA
214 concludes that that on average nitrate content in rivers has decreased by 20 percent since 2020, and
215 on average, nitrate concentrations in groundwater have not changed in 30 years (Christiansen and
216 Rouillard, 2020). In 2020 EEA also reported that on average between 2016-18 less than half of the
217 MS had no exceedance of the Nitrate limit values, while a large share of the MS had exceedance

218 between 3 and 5 percent of the drinking water bodies. In large parts of the EU the nitrate in rivers
219 has decreased since 1991.

220 Country-specific programmes for controlling pesticide use have been in place for a long time, and
221 the first EU level policy was introduced in 1979, related to authorization of pesticides, later
222 followed by regulations of hazardous waste, including pesticides. The Sustainable Use of
223 Pesticides Directive was launched in 2009 (EC/128/2009), aiming to reduce risks and impacts of
224 pesticide use on the environment and human health, by promoting integrated pest management
225 (IPM) and alternative management methods, including mechanical and other alternatives to
226 pesticides. The directive has had limited success with regards to reducing pesticide use (Eurostat
227 2021). At individual MS level various tax schemes have been used (Belgium, Denmark, France,
228 Italy, Sweden), and introduction of tax schemes has also been proposed at EU level, either as a
229 uniform tax or preferably differentiated according to risk to the environment and human health
230 (Oskam et al. 1997; Skevas et al 2013). Recently, combinations of instruments, designed to address
231 the heterogeneity amongst farmers, have been recommended (Pedersen et al, 2020).

232

233 The Habitat Directive (92/43/EEC) aims to ensure the protection of species and habitat types of
234 conservation concern at EU level. Article 4 in the Directive sets out that MS are required to
235 establish Natura 2000 – a coherent network of habitats and species including site-specific
236 measures. In 2011, the EC adopted a biodiversity strategy referring to the UN Biodiversity
237 Convention, aiming at halting the loss of biodiversity by 2020. Agriculture and forestry were
238 committed to maintaining and enhancing biodiversity. Targets included that, by 2020, improved
239 status for habitats and species should be demonstrable, and at least 15 percent of degraded

240 ecosystems should be restored. The success has been questioned by among others the European
241 Court of Auditors (ECA 2020), *inter alia* because of the low measurability of the targets.

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243 The Water Framework Directive (WFD) (EC 2000/60/EC) requires MS to achieve good ecological
244 status (GES) for all waters in Europe by no later than 2027 (postponed from the initially agreed
245 deadline of 2015). The EC (2019) reports that in 2018, 74 percent of the EU groundwater bodies
246 had achieved good chemical status and 89 percent had achieved good quantitative status, (i.e. the
247 amount of groundwater). For surface waters, only 38 percent and 40 percent, respectively, are in
248 good chemical and ecological status. Only a limited number of water bodies improved status since
249 2015.

250

251 The WFD requires cost-effectiveness analyses (CEA) as part of the development of Programme of
252 Measures (PoMs) in the River Basin Management plans. Most MS have accomplished this. The
253 CEA consists of target-setting, selecting measures, estimating and ranking costs and effectiveness
254 on nutrient abatement, ranking according to a CE ratio, and selecting the most efficient
255 combination (Martin-Ortega, 2012). In many countries, integrated hydrological and economic
256 catchment models have been developed and applied to enable spatially explicit assessments of the
257 cost-effective implementation of measures to reduce aquatic nutrient loads. The EC recommends
258 systematic-quantitative cost-effectiveness assessments in all river basins in order to optimize
259 management measures.

260

261 A key achievement by the WFD is that water management and regulation in the MS have been
262 tailored to location-specific conditions in the river basins to achieve good status of the specific
263 water bodies and that cost-effective PoMs have been identified. Furthermore, it is an achievement

264 that integrated model assessment tools have been developed for systematic use. The progress of
265 implementing these measures and actions is, however, not as expected. The Commission explains
266 this by a mix of technical problems, time delays between implementation and effect, as well as
267 lack of political will (EC, 2019).

268 **Agri Environmental and Climate Schemes: AECS programme development**

269 The AECS cover climate change, water, soil and biodiversity and includes practices such as
270 conservation tillage, reduced use of chemical inputs, and management of habitats (EC 2017). By
271 the end of the 2007-2013 CAP Rural development programming period, the agricultural area
272 committed to voluntary schemes amounted to about 26 percent of the utilized agricultural area in
273 the EU-28 (Eurostat 2017), and in the next period (2014-20) this share was 22.5 percent. The
274 programme periods are not strictly comparable because of changes to the schemes. Separate
275 schemes were made for organic farming from 2014, and climate was included in the AECS from
276 2014. The share of agricultural land committed to the AECS varies considerably; in the first
277 programming period Finland and Luxembourg had shares higher than 80 percent, while Greece,
278 Denmark and Cyprus had less than 10 percent under AECS. However, these numbers only cover
279 the final year of the programming period, and do not include areas supported by national
280 programmes (ibid).

281 The AECS supported by the CAP generally follow two different intervention logics (Röder and
282 Matthews, 2021). Some aim to encourage farmers to modify their practices to become more
283 environmentally friendly and reduce their environmental impacts (Table 1, Column A). Others
284 seek to support existing practices, delivering cultural or environmental services, that are not
285 economically sustainable in the long run (Table 1, Column B). These two types of interventions

286 can be implemented in different contexts. For illustration purposes, it can be useful to divide these
 287 into two different contexts, one where the counterfactual is an intensification of agricultural
 288 practices (Table 1, Row I), another where the counterfactual is extensification i.e. reducing
 289 agricultural inputs or even land abandonment (Table 1, Row II). The first context (I) is generally
 290 the case for many lowland arable and animal intensive systems in the western and central Europe.
 291 The second context (II) is more typical for mountainous grassland systems. Note that while we are
 292 here interested primarily in the environmental (including biodiversity) and climate outcome the
 293 cultural importance is often a priority.

294 Table 1: Intervention logics under different counterfactual situations (adapted from Röder and
 295 Matthews, 2021)

		AECS intervention:	
		Modify existing practices (A)	Preserve existing farming systems (B)
Counterfactual: Threat to agri- environmental outcomes	Intensification (I)	AI	BI
	Extensification (II)	AII	BII

296 Notably, AECS form part of the broader family of payment for environmental services (PES) tools
 297 (Wunder et al. 2020). While incentives give agents a positive motive for ‘participating’, there are
 298 also drawbacks, notably an adverse self-selection bias towards ‘baseline-complying agents’.
 299 Farmers who would have (fully or nearly) complied with scheme targets even without a payment

300 -whether due to intrinsic environmental motivations or economic constraints to maximize land
301 rents (e.g. lack of labour) – will also be the first to sign up for incentives. They will thus receive a
302 reward for their good environmental behaviour, but their entrance and payment will not be
303 ‘additional’, i.e. not making a difference to the environmental impacts of the AECS (Persson and
304 Alpizar 2013).

305 The situation characterized as BII might generally be the most straightforward case for a support
306 program, as the programme developer only needs to identify the land management practices
307 required to achieve the desired environmental output. The farmers have no incentives to exert more
308 effort than is prescribed by the programme. If the effort employed is observable to the regulator,
309 such programmes can be relatively simple to develop and monitor.

310 For the other situations, it can be more challenging. For BI, the situation is prone to more conflict
311 of interest between the principal and the farmer. In situations where maintaining the environmental
312 good requires that landscape features are not removed, such as hedge rows, ponds and groves of
313 environmental and cultural significance, cross-compliance may provide sufficient security of
314 continued environmental protection. However, where the environmental outcome requires active
315 land management, the compensation payments to ensure that participation rates are sufficiently
316 high need to be balanced against windfall effects. As an example, for carbon storage in soils where
317 avoiding tilling can be an effective measure, longevity of the effects are compromised when the
318 interventions are merely temporary. Sequestration of carbon in soils and above ground biomass is
319 a slow process, and the carbon stocks are quickly released when the contract period to prevent
320 emissions runs out. The same is the case for biodiversity conservation objectives where the value

321 of a specific site could quickly be diminished through a single event compromising habitats and
322 species.

323 In the situations under A, where farmers are required to change behaviour, a long list of additional
324 challenges are introduced. We review the literature on the behavioural factors determining the
325 farmers participation behaviour in the penultimate section of the paper. Here we merely highlight
326 that scheme interventions and farmers' motivations to adopt the schemes cover very different types
327 of economic decisions, varying from investment decisions in biogas plants to reduce GHG
328 emissions and decisions to set aside of agricultural land to reduce emissions of nutrients to
329 introduction of pesticide free agricultural systems (ECA, 2021).

330 The contractual mechanisms of AECS schemes have been of high research interest and it has been
331 hypothesised that the existing ones, commonly based on fixed per-hectare payments for stipulated
332 agri-environmental practices (or actions) are likely to be ineffective. This has led to proposals to
333 design schemes where payments would be based on the results achieved rather than proxies serving
334 as inputs into those results (Hanley and White, 2014). The main argument for implementing
335 results-based schemes has been that they will encourage farmers to align their effort better with
336 the objectives of the scheme. Furthermore, such schemes will also give incentives for farmers to
337 innovate, and give them more flexibility to achieve the environmental target (Moxey and White,
338 2014). These theoretical perspectives are well-founded and the advantages and disadvantages for
339 the farmers and the regulator have been widely debated. Some results-based schemes have been
340 implemented to meet biodiversity conservation objectives (Hanley and White, 2014), and the
341 schemes have been widely promoted (Moxey and White, 2014), but have limitations where the
342 environmental outcome is complex, risky, and/or robust indicators are either infeasible or costly

343 to monitor (Matzdorf and Lorenz, 2010). To our knowledge, results-based schemes have not been
344 implemented for water or climate objectives in Europe. Some scientific studies analyse
345 hypothetical schemes, designing and suggesting result-based payment schemes for nonpointsource
346 pollution abatement from arable land (Bartkowski et al 2021), based on modelled outcomes of
347 pollution abatement to overcome the monitoring problem related to non-point pollution. The
348 concerns over the inefficiency of uniform fixed payment practice schemes have also resulted in
349 proposals for reverse auction-based schemes, but such mechanisms have not yet been widely
350 adopted as a mechanism in agri-environmental schemes in Europe although well tested for
351 allocation of agricultural production permits. Given the central role of AECS in European
352 agrienvironmental policy, we now turn to the established evidence for the impact of these schemes.

353 **Environmental-economic impact evaluation of the voluntary schemes**

354 The design of AECS and the measurement of their effectiveness must take into account the
355 intervention logic and the bottom-line added value of the programme, also referred to as
356 ‘environmental additionality ‘ (Table 1). It is well-known from the broader literature that,
357 compared to other sectors, environmental conservation in general has been little pre-occupied with
358 rigorous measurements of quantitative impacts – ‘rigorous ‘ here referring to the use of
359 experimental or quasi-experimental techniques that specify a well-defined counterfactual baseline
360 to answer the question: ‘what would likely have happened in the absence of the environmental
361 intervention?’ (Ferraro and Pattanayak 2006). Notably, this goes beyond the monitoring and
362 evaluation of CAP performance against its objectives under the common framework CMEF
363 (Common Monitoring and Evaluation Framework CMEF) set up by the EC (2017) and conducted
364 by MS (EC 2017).

365 Impact evaluation as a scientific field of study has developed considerably over the last decades
366 (Gertler et al. 2016). In the context of AECS, at least two aspects are important: i) whether the
367 scheme and implemented measures lead to an effect in the environment, including whether the
368 scheme enhances the most cost-effective measures (actions); and ii) to what extent other objectives
369 (livelihoods, regional development, enhancing cultural heritage, etc.) are attained. Impact
370 evaluation are bottom-line assessments of additionality (environmental, socioeconomic, etc.). Here
371 we focus on the first aspect.

372 As mentioned, the voluntariness of participant self-selection into AECS can represent challenges
373 of adverse selection biases (see previous section). Therefore, uncorrected comparisons of
374 environmental performance of adopters and non-adopters, although sometimes used also in AECS
375 evaluations (e.g. Oltmer et al. 2000) does not offer a robust basis for impact evaluation: typically,
376 it will overestimate environmental impacts. As the impact evaluator is often only called upon
377 during or after the implementation stages, the options for correction of bias are econometric
378 strategies to post-correct for participant selection biases. Imbens and Woolbridge (2009) give a
379 useful overview of the theoretical and empirical consideration for the choice of identification
380 approach in applied work. It is important to highlight that by using impact evaluation
381 methodologies and experimental pilot testing as part of development of new AECS and reform of
382 existing schemes, more options are available and critical knowledge about how to design more
383 effective AECS could be obtained.

384 Given the substantial budget of the CAP, the environmental objectives and the advances in the
385 literature on impact evaluation, it might therefore be surprising that limited information exists on
386 the environmental economic effectiveness of the AECS funded under the CAP (Zimmerman and
387 Britz, 2016). To better understand why this might be the case, we divide the analysis into the

388 various aspects of environmental and economic impact of the AECS. This helps reveal the gaps in
389 knowledge and offers insights for improvement of environmental and economic performance of
390 the AECS. We divide this into i) evaluation of environmental effectiveness, ii) cost-effectiveness
391 and iii) behavioural impacts, ie. the extent to which sufficient uptake of existing AECS has been
392 achieved.

393 *Environmental effectiveness of AECS*

394 The current environmental objective of the AECS under the CAP focuses on climate, biodiversity,
395 soil and water. The review by Kleijn and Sutherland (2003) is widely cited as the first study to
396 conduct a comprehensive assessment of ecological effectiveness of AECS in Europe in terms of
397 their effect on biodiversity. They concluded that for half of the programmes, no biodiversity impact
398 could be identified. Since then, several European wide reviews (collated in Batary et al. 2015) have
399 shown that European AECS have generally been beneficial for farmland biodiversity. The
400 evaluations have used a quasi-experimental approach comparing fields enrolled in AECS with
401 control fields to identify species/taxa-specific and landscape level factors determining the
402 effectiveness of scheme interventions. The landscape context has been of particular importance in
403 the European evaluation due to its high proportion of agricultural land use (Batary et al. 2015), i.e.
404 the evaluations have been focused on AI and BI contexts (Table 1). The research has shown that
405 ecological effectiveness of AECS can be enhanced by targeting intensively farmed landscapes of
406 intermediate spatial complexity, and that interventions outside the main production areas (such as
407 field margins and hedgerows) are more effective than changing management practices on the fields
408 (such as changing cropping patterns) (Batary et al, 2011, 2015, Scheper, J. et al 2013). Batary et
409 al. (2015) hypothesise that in such landscapes AECS can provide natural resources for the

410 surrounding farmland and also provide buffers for protected habitats. They do, however, observe
411 that there is no evidence to suggest that the AECS have become more effective over time and that
412 the evidence is geographically biased towards intensively farmed landscapes in the UK, Northern
413 and Western Europe. They provide some evidence that AECS implemented in the less intensive
414 system in Eastern Europe might in fact have been environmentally counterproductive.

415 AECS to improve water quality includes measures such as short- and long-term set-aside land,
416 field margins, buffer zones, catch crops, reforestation, wetland restoration, conversion to grassland
417 and reduced fertiliser applications are. These measures are all more or less effective for protection
418 of groundwater, freshwater bodies as well as the marine environment, depending on the natural
419 specific conditions, the location and the agricultural history of the land. Several studies show that
420 AECS can deliver reductions in diffuse pollution caused by e.g. excess nutrients from agriculture,
421 but that these benefits are not evenly distributed across the landscape (Jones et al, 2017, Balana et
422 al 2011, Hasler et al 2019). Jones et al also conclude that even though improved water quality is
423 an expected effect of AECS it has not yet been demonstrated, but that spatially targeted AECS
424 implementation is likely to be most effective at delivering water quality improvements.

425 The focus on climate in the CAP is relatively more recent (since 2013), but the latest CAP period
426 2014-2020 does provide insight into the priorities given to mitigation of climate impacts. The
427 recently published report from the European Court of Auditors (ECA, 2021) provides a compelling
428 intuitive case for the lack of positive environmental impact of the AECS: the emissions have not
429 declined since 2010. Furthermore, support actions even incentivize high-impact activities, and
430 supported measures under the AECS generally have little potential for climate mitigation. The
431 report does not employ rigorous impact evaluation methodologies, but as the lack of progress on

432 the before-after indicators is clear, it seems convincing that the CAP has not delivered on the stated
433 climate policy ambition. Pe'er et al. (2017, p. 3) support this conclusion and argues that, even if
434 there are local and regional AECS, 'they fail to scale up to the EU level and the CAP as a whole.
435 Main inhibitors are limited budget, low uptake, and poor design and implementation '.

436 *Cost-effectiveness of AECS*

437 Logically, evaluation of cost-effectiveness of AECS requires not only assessment of the
438 environmental effectiveness, but also the costs. In their original study of the effectiveness of AECS
439 for biodiversity outcomes, Kleijn and Sutherland (2003) found that none of the reviewed 62 studies
440 provided any information on costs. An overview of 2000 restoration studies found that none of
441 the studies conducted a cost-effectiveness analysis and only 5 percent provided cost data, that could
442 be used for evaluation purposes (TEEB 2009). In a more recent review, Ansell et al (2015)
443 concluded that the AECS evaluation literature in conservation biology still pays limited attention
444 to costs. It is also worth noting that AECS involve different types of costs, ranging from
445 opportunity costs of agricultural production, to costs of biodiversity-enhancing activities and
446 administrative and transaction costs.

447 As mentioned, the WFD requires cost-effectiveness analyses as part of the River Basin
448 Management plans. Developed CEA tools have the potential to be linked to the AECS development
449 and guide decisions of how AECS can be designed to be more cost-effective in achieving water
450 quality objectives (Bartkowski et al 2021).

451 The introduction of climate objectives into the AECS is relatively recent, but ex-ante analyses of
452 climate-focused schemes have suggested that carbon sequestration in soils could potentially offer

453 cost-effective options. Yet, emissions from animal-intensive productions and lack of cost-effective
454 options remains a challenge.

455 *Uptake of AECS*

456 Zimmerman and Britz (2016) use FADN data of 155,516 sample farms across 22 EU MS surveyed
457 from 2000-2009 to assess uptake. The countries missing from the sample were Bulgaria, Romania,
458 Cyprus, Greece and Lithuania because counts on AECS program participation were not available.
459 AECS targeted at managing grasslands and semi-natural forage areas are the schemes being most
460 frequently taken up by farmers s, followed by input management and support to develop
461 management plans. Soil cover, soil management, buffer zones, crop management and landscape
462 feature management are also types of measures represented, but less frequent. These categories are
463 more frequently represented in the western than the eastern part of the EU (Zimmerman and Britz
464 2016). Zimmerman and Britz (ibid) also describe that the AECS payments range from high (above
465 300 EUR/ha) in Malta, Cyprus, the Netherlands, Greece, Estonia, Austria, and Luxembourg, to
466 low (under 100 EUR/ha) in Romania, Poland, Bulgaria, Spain, France and the UK.

467 To date, little is known about whether uptake of AECS actually improves the environmental
468 performance of farms overall, and whether there is an economic payoff from implementation of
469 more sustainable farming practices, supported by the schemes. Only a few studies have attempted
470 to measure empirically the impact of European AECS participation on farm-level economic
471 performance. Even fewer have attempted to compare these benefits with any non-market benefits
472 targeted by the schemes and the costs of the scheme including administrative and transaction costs.
473 In recent years, an increasing body of work has attempted to apply more robust impact evaluation
474 techniques to European AECS. As explained above, as AECS are voluntary, the uptake of schemes

475 might also be driven by environmental motivations of the farmers, suggesting that sustainable
476 farming practices might have been implemented at least to some extent in the absence of the AECS.
477 In presence of this selection bias, a direct comparison of participating with non-participating farms
478 will not represent the true causal impact of the policy. Furthermore, reduction of environmental
479 and climate impacts in a field might occur jointly with increased environmental and climate
480 impacts elsewhere on the farm (on-farm leakage). Therefore, field-level analysis may be
481 misleading; farm- and landscape-scale evaluations are likely to give a more accurate account of
482 impacts. To give a few illustrative examples of the results from farm-level analyses, Chabé-Ferret
483 and Subervie (2013) compared the environmental additionality and windfall effects across five
484 AECS in France. Their results suggested the schemes might not be cost-effective. However, the
485 comparison between schemes showed that specific schemes imposing strong requirements, such
486 as the ones aiming to subsidize conversion to organic farming, had large additionality, and almost
487 no windfall effects. Udagawa et al. (2014) analysed the Entry Level Stewardship (ELS) scheme in
488 eastern England. They found that participation in the ELS scheme negatively affected farm
489 incomes, suggesting that the ELS payment did not fully compensate for costs incurred in the first
490 years of participation. Mennig and Sauer (2020) found AECS to have different effects on dairy
491 and arable crop farms in Bavaria: AECS designed for arable land overcompensate farmers,
492 whereas for the dairy farms the AECS were potentially too restrictive preventing farmers from
493 participating. Bertoni et al (2020) analysed three AECS implemented in the Lombardy Region
494 (Italy). They conclude that the AECS are effective in improving environmental performances of
495 farms. However, their preliminary cost-benefit analysis indicates that the costs of implementing
496 schemes tend to be high vis-à-vis the additional environmental impact. Arata and Sckokai (2016)
497 is perhaps the only study applying a robust econometric impact evaluation approach to assess the

498 impact of AECS on farmers' environmental and economic performance across different EU
499 countries. Their results suggest that AECS impacts vary across countries, depending on the
500 importance of the AECS payment in the overall farm income: when the share of AECS payments
501 on farm income is smaller than 5 percent, farmers' practices change only marginally.

502 **Barriers and potentials: what drives farmers participation in the AECS**

503 Limited uptake of environmentally effective AECS has been one of the key proximate causes for
504 the deficient progress on environmental and climate objectives in European agriculture. As
505 voluntary AECS is an important mechanism for achieving these objectives, it is important to
506 identify the underlying factors that determine farmers' participation in AECS. Understanding these
507 determinants gives information about both the barriers to and the potential for successful program
508 uptake. We draw on a number of meta-reviews that attempt to synthesise the many single studies
509 in the literature into systematic knowledge about the key drivers of farmers' decisions to join
510 agrienvironmental and climate schemes or, more broadly, to take up sustainable practices (see for
511 instance, Wilson 2000; Lastla-Brava et al 2015; Dessart et al 2019; Bartkowski and Bartke 2018).
512 The meta-reviews include studies covering both ex-ante studies surveying willingness to accept
513 compensation for changing agricultural practices and ex-post studies typically using survey data
514 or qualitative interviews to reveal underlying motivations and behavioural drivers of adoption and
515 non-adoption.

516 Across the meta studies the following main categories of determinants emerge: farm-related factors
517 such as size or farm-type, farmer-demographics and features related to the design of specific
518 AECS. Economic incentives played an important role in farmers' decisions to participate in

519 schemes across a wide range of studies, but other factors were also at play (see Lastra-Bravo et al.
520 2015, Bartkowski and Bartke 2018; Dessart et al 2019, Wilson and Hart 2000).

521 A consistent finding across the literature is that farmers who are driven by environmental or
522 conservation values are more likely to adopt a sustainable practice associated with an AECS
523 (Lastra-Bravo et al 2015; Dessart et al 2019; Bartkowski and Bartke 2018). Farmers who invoke
524 moral concerns related to nature conservation are also more likely to participate. In addition to
525 these direct motivations for participation, farmers' uptake of schemes is also affected by the
526 objectives the farmer generally pursues in relation to his farming practice. Farmers, who strongly
527 prioritize economic objectives, are less likely to engage in sustainable practices, according to all
528 four studies cited in Dessart et al (2019). Likewise, farmers who are production oriented and pursue
529 a yield optimization strategy will be less interested in AECS that could reduce yield (Brown et al.
530 2019; Pedersen et al 2011). On the other hand, farmers who pursue lifestyle and conservation
531 objectives in their farming are more likely to join a scheme (Dessart et al 2019; Brown et al. 2019).
532 However, we would expect the match between farmer motivation and AECS participation to be
533 conditional on features of the AECS. Most of the AECS examined in the behavioural literature
534 focus on reduced-intensity schemes, either changing practices (cf. AI in table 1), e.g. reducing
535 nitrate input or adopting organic practices, or preserving landscape features such as hedge rows
536 (BI in table 1). For these types of schemes, production and economically oriented farmers are less
537 likely to join, although economic motivation could be accommodated through high payments. Yet,
538 as mentioned above, Type A AECS may also include new technology schemes, which may align
539 with motivation types in different ways than practice changes. E.g. investments in biogas facilities
540 would allow the farmer to maintain production levels and even provide a higher quality manure,
541 while at the same time reducing greenhouse gas emissions from manure. Such schemes might

542 therefore be more likely to attract also economically oriented farmers. Continue-to-farm schemes
543 (AII and BII) would appear less attractive to production-oriented farmers and could be an
544 explanation for lack of uptake, while farmers motivated by environmental or conservation
545 objectives might be more interested in these schemes.

546 Risk tolerance, which may be considered a general personality feature not specifically related to
547 AECS, also influences farmers' willingness to engage in new practices, including organic farming
548 (Dessart et al 2019; Bartkowski and Bartke 2018). In relation to AECS a farmer's degree of risk
549 tolerance or risk aversion, respectively, may affect how the farmer reacts to perceived risks to
550 either economic outcome or physical yield from participating in a scheme. Implementing results-
551 orientated AECS may therefore run into problems with farmers who have a low tolerance for risk
552 (Burton and Schwarz 2013), unless risk distribution between farmers and regulators is taken into
553 account.

554 Moreover, the perceived impacts that farmers associate with the programs, be they financial,
555 environmental, or work planning related, have been shown to affect enrolment in programs and
556 uptake of sustainable practices (Dessart et al 2019). The key is that these are costs and benefits as
557 perceived by the farmer rather than objective costs and benefits. It is well-established that
558 individuals act on perceived costs and benefits, and these may not reflect objective costs very well
559 due to cognitive biases such as a higher valuation of present costs and benefits over future ditto
560 and loss aversion which implies that losses count more than gains of the same numeric value .

561 Such biases have also been identified in farmers' decision-making (Vanslebrouck et al 2002;
562 Yeboah et al 2015). Important in this context, therefore, is the fact that experience with AECS
563 appears to be a powerful factor in farmers' decision to enroll again or in new programs

564 (LastraBravo et al 2015). Having experience would affect perceptions of costs and benefits and
565 may therefore align decision parameters better with objective costs and benefits.

566 AECS enrolment may be influenced by social factors. Thus, in experimental surveys both
567 collective bonuses offered to farmers on the condition that a certain number of farmers participate
568 in a scheme and social nudges, offering information that other farmers intend to participate, have
569 shown to increase farmers' willingness to enroll or remain in the scheme (Kuhfuss et al 2016).

570 Farm-related factors also affect enrollment. Thus, interest in AECS appears to increase with the
571 size of the farm, although some studies find the opposite (Lastra-Bravo et al. 2015). A consistent
572 finding across the literature is that livestock farmers with large shares of grassland are more likely
573 to participate in schemes than crop farmers (Lastra-Bravo et al 2015; Bartkowski and Bartke 2018).
574 Most likely, this is due to another important determinant of participation, namely the fit of the
575 scheme with existing practices on the farm. Extensively farmed areas may be more compatible
576 with certain schemes and therefore require less significant changes in farming practices, which
577 reduces barriers for entry of lowers the remuneration rate farmers are willing to accept to enroll
578 (Pavlis et al 2016; Lastra-Bravo et al 2015; Bartkowski and Bartke 2018). On the other hand, arable
579 [crop] farms tend to focus on land productivity and are therefore less likely to show an interest in
580 extensification or other measures that reduce production (Lastra-Bravo et al 2015; Wilson and Tart
581 2000). Yet, for some measures such as catch crops, crop farmers at least in Northern Europe may
582 actually require lower compensation than livestock farmers, because catch crops fit their farming
583 practices better (Haslet et al 2019). Thus, there is considerable heterogeneity in the match between
584 farm types and specific AECS measures, implying that barriers and potentials vary for different
585 schemes.

586 Finally, scheme designs are – obviously - influential. Level of remuneration is a key determinant
587 in uptake. Typically, farmers require compensation that covers not only productivity losses, but
588 also transaction costs and possibly a risk premium (Haslet et al. 2019, Christensen et al. 2011).
589 This implies also that required compensation levels are conditional on scheme features. Schemes
590 that allow for shorter time commitments and flexible implementation requirements are more
591 popular among farmers which increases enrolment and typically lower the WTA (Lastra-Bravo et
592 al 2015; Bartkowski and Bartke 2018; Christensen et al 2011). At the same time, policy stability,
593 that is minimizing changes to policy content and scheme requirements over several funding
594 periods, is important to reduce farmers’ uncertainty about enrollment (Lastra-Bravo et al 2015;
595 Defrancesco et al 2008). In addition to design, availability of information, for instance through
596 farm advisory services, affects farmers’ participation.

597 A final point is that the influence of these determinants and in AECS in general may vary across
598 countries. In a comparative survey, Pavlis et al (2016) found that farmers in Northern Europe were
599 generally more interested in participating than farmers in Central and Southern Europe.

600 While some of the barriers to participation in schemes, including farm characteristics, cannot be
601 changed per se, knowledge about behavioural factors may constitute potential. AECS can then be
602 designed to fit farmer motivation and cognition, or by design of information to influence
603 perceptions of costs, benefits and risks, at least to the extent where these perceptions do not match
604 objective conditions. A key recommendation from the literature is to include stakeholders in design
605 of schemes to improve match between decision makers and schemes.

606 **Summary and conclusions**

607 The new European agri-environmental policy recently adopted (EC, 2021), has a stated ambition
608 to integrate environmental and climate legislation into the CAP. The new policy reform is an
609 opportunity for developing a more coherent policy and implementation, taking the experiences
610 from former reforms into account to deliver better in respect to the environmental and climate
611 objectives.

612 One factor explaining the dominance of income support is agricultural exceptionalism, i.e. the
613 political belief that farming is an exceptional and hazardous industry because it is exposed to
614 unpredictable and unstable weather and market conditions, and that this justifies exceptional
615 policies for agriculture. This perspective can partly explain the limited environmental
616 improvements despite the CAP reforms, where evaluations of the directives (the Nitrate Directive,
617 the WFD, the Habitat Directive and the Sustainable Pesticide Directive) illustrate significant gaps
618 in the delivery of the objectives.

619 Another factor explaining the gaps in the achievement of the objectives and targets set in the
620 directives is that it is highly dependent on the policy instruments of the CAP, i.e. the AECS, the
621 greening and cross-compliance. Existing and past AECS implemented in EU28 are diverse, and
622 evaluation of the environmental and economic performance and impacts is challenged as detailed
623 data on the type of scheme, eligibility, payment levels and agricultural practices or outcomes
624 involved are not systematically collected. There are a growing number of ex-ante studies on
625 scheme characteristics, but few ex-post studies evaluate the environmental effectiveness or
626 costeffectiveness of the programmes.

627 In the design of new AECS or redesign of existing schemes balancing the costs of the programme,
628 behavioural response and targeted environmental effect continues to challenge programme
629 developers. Development of different forms of contractual mechanisms of the schemes is likely to
630 provide some of the answers to improved effectiveness. Existing AECS have largely been based
631 on fixed hectare payments for stipulated agri-environmental practices (or actions). The result of
632 this non-targeted use of AECS in EU28 is that, while addressing a wide range of environmental
633 problems and externalities, the focus has been on paying farmers for the farming processes. Hereby
634 the EU AECS have been easy to use as an income transfer mechanism to producers.

635 Improved spatial targeting can be achieved by development of result-based AECS, for which there
636 is an emerging interest in the EU. Findings from experimenting with results-based payments (cf.
637 e.g. the Results Based Environment-Agri Pilot Project (REAP) in Ireland) can potentially offer
638 insights to better incentivize cost-effective practices. Identifying the context where such results
639 based AECS are more cost-effective and developing policy tools to manage the additional
640 monitoring and verification needs without incurring infeasible administrative costs appears to be
641 important for research and practice going forward. Monitoring and measurements can lead to an
642 increase of the administrative and transaction costs, but integrated modelling for decision support
643 can be used as a supplement to achieve a shift from action-based to result-based targeted use of
644 the schemes. Uptake may also be improved by providing more different types of AECS to target
645 more broadly farmers, who vary with regards to motivation for farming and therefore for enrolling
646 in AECS. Likewise, policymakers may more explicitly design AECS based on available
647 knowledge about behavioural barriers and potential for enrollment.

648 Matching AECS uptake to spatially heterogeneous and spatially interdependent requirements for
649 pro-environmental action highlights the limitations of AECS based only on contracts with

650 individual farmers. AECS involving collaborative contracts is a potential answer that has been
651 proposed based on modelling studies testing different forms of payments for collaborative
652 behaviour, and which has also been tested in behavioural experiments. The results are encouraging;
653 however, to date very limited experiences exist in real agricultural landscapes.

654 The experiences from the greening and cross-compliance are that the link between the
655 environmental regulations and the CAP income support has watered down the ambitions by the
656 MS and that the environmental effects have been modest. These experiences are so far not reflected
657 in the introduction of the new eco-schemes, that MS need too design and implement.

658 Further emphasis on developing the AECS paying farmers for the provision of public goods seems
659 to be the best way forward, but each part of the agri-environmental policy has its own objectives
660 and while targeted achievement is necessary, it is not easy.

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